

PREDICTING THE VALUE OF INDOOR CO₂ CONCENTRATION IN A UNIVERSITY AUDITORIUM USING A DECISION TREE ALGORITHM AND A DATA MINING METHOD

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The aim of this study is to predict the CO₂ concentration levels based on data obtained in the auditorium of the new university building of the Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy and Faculty of Forestry (FACEG-FF) at the University of Banja Luka in correlation to the operation of the mechanical ventilation system. The data used for the analysis were collected from measurements and surveys on students' subjective perception of indoor thermal and air quality. Data analysis and statistical processing were carried out using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS). The influence of measured physical parameters and the impact of user behaviour on CO₂ concentration using the chi-square automatic interaction detection (CHAID) decision tree technique in a university auditorium was predicted. The dataset comprised 11 input variables (A1–A11), a continuous output variable representing CO₂ concentration (B1, ppm), and two predicted categorical outputs: B2, describing CO₂ concentration classes, and B3, indicating air quality satisfaction based on a 1000 ppm CO₂ threshold. Classification accuracy was between 89.2% and 97.5% for dependent variable B2 (class of indoor air quality) and 94.2% and 99.2% for dependent variable B3 (satisfactory - value below or above 1000 ppm CO₂). The findings indicate that maintaining CO₂ levels below 1000 ppm is crucial for ensuring satisfactory indoor air quality and thermal comfort among occupants.

Key words: CO₂, Air Comfort, Thermal Comfort, Ventilation Mode, Predict, Decision Tree

1. Introduction

Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) is defined as the quality of air within buildings and their surrounding areas, with respect to its effects on occupant health and comfort. It has been influenced by carbon dioxide

(CO₂) concentration, primarily released by human respiration, and correlated to thermal comfort. Since indoor environments are influenced by building characteristics, ventilation strategies, and occupant behaviour, IAQ has become a key factor in creating healthy and comfortable indoor spaces. Real-time monitoring of indoor air quality (IAQ) parameters and occupant behaviour is essential for improving indoor environmental conditions, protecting public health, enhancing occupants' well-being [1–5], and ensuring adequate building performance, particularly given that people in the EU spend around 90% of their time indoors. The European Union is increasingly recognising this importance, supporting the development and improvement of legislation, as seen in recent initiatives to align air quality standards with World Health Organization (WHO) recommendations and improve the scientific basis for policy.

Thermal comfort is a subjective phenomenon that can display large differences among individual occupants [6]. Thermal comfort and indoor air quality are key factors that significantly influence students' perceptions of the indoor environment while interacting with building ventilation systems and corresponding energy consumption. Adequate ventilation can guarantee thermal comfort and indoor air quality for building occupants, and current mechanical ventilation systems have enormous potential to reduce energy consumption with the help of natural ventilation and optimal control strategies [7–9]. Environmental parameters such as temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, CO₂ concentration, and running mean outdoor temperature demonstrate stronger correlations with thermal responses than with IAQ responses. In studies of non-residential buildings with natural ventilation, the results of CO₂ concentration confirm that good sealing of building envelopes and user behavior affect air quality and that there is a very strong correlation between CO₂ parameters and relative humidity and indoor air temperature. This research indicates that the key input parameters in CO₂ prediction models are: relative humidity, air temperature, number of people in the room, occupancy pattern, and ventilation mode. [10–13].

Increasing CO₂ concentration leads to higher thermal sensation, reduced thermal preference, and reduced perceived control [14]. In contrast, IAQ responses show no significant variations with changes in indoor operative temperature [14]. An effective ventilation system should ensure an adequate fresh air supply to ensure indoor air quality while simultaneously regulating indoor temperature to maintain optimal thermal comfort. Poor ventilation can negatively affect both indoor air quality (e.g., high level of CO₂ concentration) and thermal comfort (e.g., perceived stuffiness). Furthermore, inadequate airflow creates a stagnant environment causing occupants to feel excessively warm. This connection means that a strategy to improve one can help or hinder the other, highlighting the need for holistic approaches to manage indoor environmental quality (IEQ) [15–18]. The need to control CO₂ concentration by adjusting HVAC system settings to maintain a satisfactory indoor environment has also been suggested by health research on how CO₂ concentration affects occupants. Increasing indoor CO₂ levels between 550 and 950 ppm negatively affect occupant cognitive performance [19], occupant productivity decreases significantly as CO₂ concentration increases from 600 ppm to 1000 ppm [20], and when CO₂ concentration exceeds 1000 ppm, symptoms of discomfort such as nausea, dizziness, and fatigue occur [21]. Therefore, CO₂ concentration was used in this study as an indicator of indoor air quality.

Buildings consume a large amount of energy and emit significant amounts of greenhouse gases to maintain a comfortable thermal environment for occupants. Many studies have shown that energy-efficient or low-energy buildings require the use of passive design solutions to reduce energy consumption and that this can improve indoor comfort conditions. However, existing inefficient indoor

climate control strategies can lead to overheating and cooling of indoor spaces in both hot and cold climates, affecting occupant productivity and well-being and leading to excessive energy costs [22].

Although modern ensemble models such as Random Forest and XGBoost often achieve high predictive accuracy and dominate recent literature [23], interpretable machine learning approaches remain important in studies related to building performance and indoor environmental quality. Decision tree-based methods provide transparent rule-based structures that enable direct interpretation of relationships between predictor variables and system outputs [24–26], whereas complex models such as artificial neural networks are often considered “black-box” models despite their strong predictive capabilities [27]. In this study, the CHAID (Chi-square Automatic Interaction Detection) algorithm was selected because it enables statistically significant data segmentation using χ^2 tests and effectively handles categorical variables [28, 29]. In addition, decision tree approaches have been successfully applied in the analysis and prediction of building energy performance and occupant-related impacts in buildings [30, 31]. Due to its ability to generate interpretable hierarchical structures and clear decision rules, the CHAID algorithm provides valuable insights into the relationships between indoor environmental parameters and CO₂ concentration levels while maintaining relatively low model complexity.

The aim of this study is to predict the CO₂ concentration levels based on data obtained in the auditorium of the new university building of the Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy and Faculty of Forestry (FACEG-FF) at the University of Banja Luka in correlation to the operation of the mechanical ventilation system. At the same time, a survey of students was conducted regarding air quality and thermal comfort, in order to conclude whether students feel the level of CO₂ concentration and what their satisfaction is related to it. In this area of research, no one has used the aforementioned algorithm for these purposes, and the significance is to show that with the help of a decision tree and the CHAID algorithm, CO₂ concentration can be predicted.

2. Materials and methods

Data analysis for classification and regression was performed using the CHAID technique based on the Chi-square's p-value. Kass discusses only the case of a categorical dependent variable [28]. The method is, nevertheless, most often implemented with an option for handling also quantitative dependent variables [32]. CHAID was preferred for analysis because of its efficiency in large datasets, its highly visual and easy interpretation, ease of implementation, and input data quality can be handled efficiently [33, 34]. In this algorithm, homogenous groups may be formed by any possible combination of the known values of a categorical predictor, or by setting cut-off points at any values of a continuous predictor. The number of selected independent predictors for creating the model together with the number categories (for categorical and ordinal) and intervals (for continuous) for the selected independent predictors depends on results of the Chi-square analyses and whether the differences are significant or not [35]. Since the correlates of user behaviour and measured data are mixed data types, CHAID is appropriate because it uses a nonparametric procedure without assumptions about the underlying data and is designed to include continuous, ordinal, and categorical predictors/variables. In this research, CHAID analysis builds a predictive model, or tree, to help determine how variables best merge to explain the outcome in the given dependent variable.

The methodological framework of this study is illustrated in Fig. 1. The framework is based on the integration of several relevant indoor air quality and thermal comfort standards with the data sets

derived from measured parameters and survey data on students' subjective perception of indoor thermal and air quality. Combining these two data sources, a unified dataset used for data mining was created. Through this approach, the decision tree provides both a visual and analytical representation of the relative importance of each parameter and its contribution to the final air quality classification through the concentration of CO₂. The model highlights the sequence, strength, and interaction of influential variables with a goal to offer an insight into the key factors that influence indoor environmental quality in auditorium spaces. The following parameters were applied in this study: a maximum tree depth set at level 3 for the CHAID growth method, a minimum threshold for 10 cases for parent nodes and 5 cases for child nodes, a significance level of 0.05 for node splitting and category merging, the Pearson Chi-square statistic, and a maximum of 100 iterations.

Figure 1. Scheme of the methodological approach

The CHAID method creates a robust decision tree by using the χ^2 test to identify the most significant splits in the data.

The chi-square statistic is defined as [36]:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i} \quad (1)$$

where O_i represents the observed numbers and E_i represents the expected numbers. The expected values for each cell in the contingency table are calculated as follows [33]:

$$E_{ij} = \frac{O_i O_j}{O} \quad (2)$$

where O_i is the marginal frequency of the corresponding rows, O_j is the marginal relative frequency for the corresponding columns and O denotes the total number of observations. The test statistic is based on the differences between the observed and expected values [36]:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{(O_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}} \quad (3)$$

Additionally, the Independent-Samples t-test, χ^2 (chi-square) test, and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) [37] were applied to examine differences in CO₂ concentration between the two survey periods, differences in the distribution of student responses regarding temperature satisfaction and air comfort, as well as the relationship between these subjective evaluations, thereby complementing the CHAID-based modelling by enabling a direct comparison between objectively measured parameters and students' perceived indoor environmental quality.

2.1. Case study

The data sets used for the analysis in this study were collected in the auditorium of the new building of the Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy and Faculty of Forestry (FACEG-FF) of the University of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina. The building has been in use since September 2023. The annual heating energy demand is approximately 20 kWh/m² per year, placing the building in energy class "B" according to the current Regulation on Energy Audits and Certification of Buildings in the Republic of Srpska [38]. The auditorium is located in the central part of the new building, has an area of 241.48 m² and a volume of 1,117.56 m³. The central slope of the auditorium is 19°. The maximum seating capacity, including temporary chairs in the first and last rows, is 194 occupants. The minimum height of the auditorium in the upper zone is 3.10 m, while the highest part of the amphitheatre (up to the suspended ceiling) reaches 5.57 m. The walls are made of reinforced concrete without a final surface finish, while the front wall is partially clad with ceramic tiles mounted on a substructure, with thermal insulation placed in the intermediate cavity. The total wall surface area of the auditorium (including the zone between the suspended ceiling and the structural elements above the auditorium, as well as all openings) amounts to 374.36 m², of which the area of openings is 42.6 m² (11.38%). The auditorium is equipped with a system of mechanical ventilation that supplies 4250 m³/h of fresh air. Heating and cooling of the amphitheatre are regulated with an air-conditioning system (variable refrigerant volume control – VRV system), while the fresh air is provided by a ventilation unit equipped with a rotary recuperator heat wheel.

2.2. Data collection of thermal and air comfort - surveys and measurements

The data for this study were collected from two sources: subjective user perceptions and measurements of thermal and air comfort parameters. The operating mode of the mechanical ventilation system was also recorded to account for its influence on thermal comfort and indoor air quality. To ensure the analysis was consistent with established indoor air quality guidelines, the study was guided by the ASHRAE 62.1 standard [39], which provides recommendations for ventilation rates and air

quality criteria in occupied spaces. When the mechanical ventilation system was in operation a continuous fresh air supply of 4250 m³/h was provided, corresponding to at least 6.08 l/s per person, and 4.89 l/s per m², which exceeds the minimum ventilation rates prescribed by the standard.

The period during which users (students in the auditorium) were present was selected for the analysis of the indoor air quality. Users were surveyed twice over two consecutive weeks, on two days per week (Monday for first year- students and Tuesday for second-year students) using methodology defined in the EN ISO 7730 [40]. Surveys were collected under two ventilation system operating modes: when the mechanical ventilation system was turned *off* (126 students surveyed) and with the mechanical ventilation system turned *on* (110 students surveyed). The survey questionnaires were extended to obtain more detailed feedback on thermal satisfaction with students asked to rate their satisfaction with indoor temperature using a seven-point scale ranging from -3 (completely dissatisfied) to +3 (completely satisfied).

In addition to surveys, physical parameters relevant to thermal comfort including air temperature, relative humidity, air velocity and CO₂ concentration were measured during the winter period, from February 17 to March 1 2025, in accordance with the standards ISO 7726 [41]. The CO₂ concentration classes used for further analysis were derived from the recorded absolute values and divided into three classes. Since the outdoor CO₂ concentration was not considered, these classes do not correspond to the CO₂ concentration categories defined in EN 16798-1 [42].

Figure 2. Axonometry of the auditorium showing the positions of the installed measurement equipment

The measuring device was positioned at a sufficient distance from the occupants to avoid locally elevated readings and away from locations where fresh air could enter the space, which could result in locally reduced CO₂ concentrations. Technical specifications of the measurement device are listed in Table 1. The device used for measuring the thermal comfort parameters and CO₂ concentration was positioned in the centre of the room, at a height of 130 cm above the floor, and at a distance greater than 100 cm from the occupants (Fig. 2). Six temperature sensors were symmetrically distributed to cover

the entire space, while the centrally positioned sensors were used to measure the temperature, air velocity, relative humidity, and CO₂ concentration (Fig. 2). Since the auditorium is located in the central part of the building and it is surrounded by access corridors (which are also indoor spaces), the analysis was limited to the measured indoor CO₂ concentrations within the auditorium.

Table 1. Technical specifications of the measurement instruments

Device	Collection of Data	Range (Unit)	Resolution	Accuracy
Testo 435-2 with IAQ and air velocity probe	CO ₂ Concentration	0–10000 ppm	1 ppm CO ₂	± (0 – 5000 ppm CO ₂ : 75 ppm CO ₂ + 3%)
	Relative Humidity	0% to 100%	0.1 %	
	Indoor Air Temperature	-20 °C to +70 °C	0.1 °C	±3%
	Air velocity	0 to +20 m/s		± 0.5 °C
Testo 174H, Testo 174T, Testo 175T1	Relative Humidity	0% to 100%	0.1 %	±3%
	Temperature T _i	-20 °C to +70 °C	0.1 °C	± 0.5 °C

Data collection focused on monitoring parameters: carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration, temperature, relative humidity, and indoor air velocity, with respect to the duration of lectures (45-minute modules) and to the duration of breaks (15 minutes between modules) on days when student surveys were conducted. This setup provides valuable insights into the frequency and rate at which pollutant levels increase in the air since the start of the lecture. It also records how effectively and to what extent the air is being cleaned during breaks. The measurements also allow the identification of peaks, which correlate with fluctuations in the number and density of students present during lectures and when the ventilation is on – students present with and without ventilation.

The measurements were recorded in the auditorium according to the lecture schedule. Table 2 shows the total number of measurements during the survey. The same number of measurements in the first week when the ventilation was turned off and the first survey was performed (120), as well as in the second week when the ventilation was turned on and the second survey was performed (120).

Table 2. Measuring time and analysed the number of measurements of temperature and air quality parameters

Survey	Date	Measured time	Number of measurements
Survey 1	17.02.2025.	13:01 – 14:58	40
	18.02.2025.	8:01 – 11:58	80
Survey 2	24.02.2025.	13:01 – 14:58	40
	25.02.2025.	8:01 – 11:58	80

2.3. Database and decision tree

The methodological focus lies in the application of data mining techniques - decision tree modelling, to identify the relative importance and influence of each input variable on the final air quality category within the auditorium. To achieve this, all variables were statistically analysed, and the decision tree model was applied to detect patterns, dominance relationships, and hierarchical influence among the parameters. A total of 11 input variables (A1 - A11), one continuous output variable B1 (CO₂ concentration (ppm)), and two predicted output variables B2 (CO₂ concentration classification by absolute concentration value) and B3 (satisfaction with air quality depending on CO₂ concentration threshold set at 1000 ppm) were collected as presented in Table 3. All variables represent direct

parameters of thermal comfort and indoor air quality indicators. In this study, all 11 input variables (A1 - A11) derived from the data set, together with the output variables B2 and B3, were processed and analysed using three approaches: a) by processing all measured data collected on the days when the student survey was conducted, b) by processing of data corresponding to variable A9, specifically by processing the measurement data when the survey was conducted with the ventilation system was off; and c) by processing the data collected at the time of the survey with the ventilation system was on. Data analysis and statistical processing were performed using SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solutions), version 22 (IBM Corp., Armonk, USA). A significance level of $p = 0.05$ was applied.

Table 3. Database Code

Variable name	Code	Values / categories	Total	Survey1	Survey2
Mean temperature /indoor/ (°C)	A1	min:	18.8	18.8	21.7
		max:	23.6	21.5	23.6
		average:	21.63	20.43	22.83
MRT /indoor/ (°C)	A2	min:	18.6	18.6	21.4
		max:	22.8	20.5	22.8
		average:	20.97	19.76	22.19
Air flow /indoor/ (m/s)	A3	min:	0.01	0.01	0.01
		max:	0.15	0.14	0.15
		average:	0.022	0.019	0.024
Relative humidity /indoor/ (%)	A4	min:	22.85	22.85	34.54
		max:	38.88	29.89	38.88
		average:	31.38	26.13	36.56
Met	A5	1: 1.2 (sedentary activity – office, dwelling, school, laboratory) 2: 1.4 (light activity – drawing)			
Clo	A6	1: 1.18 (normal winter clothes in room) 2: 1.7 (winter cloth with jacket)			
Outdoor temperature (°C)	A7	min:	-3.6	-3.6	4.8
		max:	11.7	2.3	11.7
		average:	4.10	-0.21	8.41
Relative humidity /outdoor/ (%)	A8	min:	61.9	61.9	72
		max:	98.7	89.9	98.7
		average:	80.55	74.82	86.28
Ventilation	A9	0: Off 1: On			
Time (hh:mm)	A10	min:	08:01	08:01	08:01
		max:	14:58	14:58	14:58
Occupancy	A11	min:	53	57	53
		max:	66	66	64
		average:	58	59.92	56.76
CO ₂ (ppm)	B1	min:	453.35	453.35	456.85
		max:	1141.24	1141.24	834.82
		average:	732.75	803.82	661.67
CO ₂ concentration (class)	B2	1: < 550 ppm 2: [550 – 800) ppm 3: [800 – 1350) ppm 4: ≥ 1350 ppm			
CO ₂ concentration (satisfactory)	B3	1: < 1000 ppm /yes/ 2: ≥ 1000 ppm /no/			

All independent variables (A1 – A11) are in one node, and the dependent variable is B2. The CHAID method merges categories that are not statistically significantly different, creates a contingency table for each independent variable, and applies a χ^2 (chi-square) test to examine association between each independent variable and the dependent variable (B2), yielding a corresponding p-value. The variable with the lowest p-value is selected to split a node, which may result in multiple branches. For each newly created node, all remaining independent variables are re-evaluated using the χ^2 test. The tree continues to grow until no statistically significant split can be identified, the node has insufficient data or the maximum depth of the tree is reached. The independent variable with the lowest p-value was A1.

After creating the tree and generating decision rules, the procedure was repeated by forcing the inclusion of the remaining independent variables (A2 –A10). The same methodology was subsequently applied using B3 as the dependent variable.

The construction of the decision tree begins with identifying the most influential input variable. In this case, the mean temperature for four sensor positions (at heights of 10 cm, 60 cm, 110 cm, and 170 cm) (°C) shows the strongest power in separating air quality categories (Fig 3.) and is therefore selected as the root (parent) node of the tree, from which the hierarchical structure continues to develop.

Following the initial split based on temperature gradient, the algorithm proceeds with branching into child nodes, guided by the next most statistically dominant variable associated with the previous decision. This recursive partitioning process continues until the model of the terminal nodes are reached, at which point no further meaningful statistical subdivision of the dataset is possible. All 11 parameters (A1-A11) were analysed (Fig. 3). Initially, the decision tree was constructed without forcing any input variables. The algorithm predominantly selected indoor temperature for node splitting and produced up to 16 nodes, with variable A7, (outdoor temperature), appearing in the later stages of the tree. Under this configuration, the model predicted a 100% probability for CO₂ concentration class 2 (B2).

Figure 3. Generated decision tree illustrating overall hierarchical structure (top) and a selected part of the decision tree with the decision rule associated with node 16 (bottom)

In addition, a separate decision tree was generated with all input variables with B3 as the output variable, again without forcing any variables, to methodologically assess whether a CO₂ concentration of 1000 ppm is perceptible to users during the survey (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Decision tree generated for the output variable B3, without forcing any input variable

Without forcing any input variables, the decision tree branched to node 6, selecting variable A5 (metabolic rate), with a lower activity level of 1.2, as this value was more frequently represented among the surveyed occupants/users. This observation highlights the importance of forcing this variable in subsequent analyses to obtain results that are meaningful for discussion and for guiding further steps in the study.

3. Results and Discussion: Predictive Modelling

In this study, subjective assessments, specifically user satisfaction with the quality and temperature of indoor air under different modes of mechanical ventilation system are analysed. These observations provide context for discussion, alongside predictions derived from the measured physical parameters. During the first survey, 126 students were surveyed with the ventilation system turned *off*. The students rated thermal comfort with an average score of 0.75 and air quality with an average score of 0.64. During the second survey with a ventilation system turned *on*, 110 students participated. They rated thermal comfort with an average score of 1.05, and air quality with an average score of 0.88. During the first survey, 75 students (59.52%) reported being satisfied while 32 students (25.40%) were dissatisfied with thermal comfort. Furthermore, 65 students (51.59%) were satisfied with air quality, while 27 students (21.43%) were dissatisfied with thermal comfort. Additionally, 19 students (15.08%) reported being neutral regarding temperature comfort while 34 students (26.98%) reported being neutral regarding air quality. During the second survey, 76 students (69.09 %) reported satisfaction with temperature comfort and 72 (65.45%) students were satisfied with air quality. In contrast, 14 students (12.73%) were dissatisfied with temperature comfort, while 21 students (19.09%) dissatisfied with air quality. Additionally, 20 students (18.18%) were neutral regarding temperature comfort and 17 students (15.45%) were neutral regarding air quality (Fig. 5). Based on students' responses, on a scale from 0 (neutral) to +3 (completely satisfied), the overall level of satisfaction was high. When the mechanical ventilation system was in operation, students reported greater satisfaction with air temperature (87.3%)

than with air quality (80.9%). However, when the mechanical ventilation system was off, satisfaction with air quality 78.6% exceeded that with air temperature 74.6%.

Figure 5. Students' satisfaction with air temperature and air quality

The application of the Independent-Samples t-test revealed a highly statistically significant difference in CO₂ concentration in the amphitheater between the first and the second student surveys (t = 6.607; p < 0.001).

By regrouping the student responses “completely dissatisfied”, “very dissatisfied”, and “dissatisfied” into the category “dissatisfied”, and the responses “completely satisfied”, “very satisfied”, and “satisfied” into the category “satisfied”, while retaining the category “neutral”, the χ^2 test indicated a statistically significant difference between the second and the first survey for both temperature satisfaction ($\chi^2 = 9.35$; p = 0.009) and air comfort ($\chi^2 = 9.795$; p = 0.007).

Testing the association between student responses using Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient (ρ) revealed a highly statistically significant relationship between satisfaction with temperature and air comfort, both during the first survey ($\rho = 0.565$) and during the second survey ($\rho = 0.641$).

In this study, measurement data from two consecutive days across two consecutive weeks were presented and analysed and survey periods are indicated by squares in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Overview of measurements on selected days when surveyed students were present in the auditorium

During the first week, 22 measurements (18.33%) fell in class 1, 37 measurements (30.83%) in class 2 and 61 (50.83%) in class 3, and during the second week, 26 measurements (21.67%) were recorded in class 1, 91 measurements (75.83%) in class 2 and 3 measurements (2.5%) in class 3. During the first week satisfactory CO₂ concentrations were recorded in 93 cases (77.5%), while 27 cases (22.5%) were classified as unsatisfactory.

During the second week, all recorded CO₂ concentrations were within the satisfactory range. Continuous measurements over the 12-day period indicated CO₂ concentrations reaching up to 2,312.7 ppm (Fig. 6). However, the days selected for analysis were evaluated under controlled conditions, with a known number of users and specified ventilation operation. The indoor concentrations of CO₂ (B1) values during the first week (first survey) ranged from 453.35 to 1,141.24 ppm, while during the second week (second survey), they ranged from 456.8 to 834.8 ppm. By introducing the variable B2 and classes derived from the EN 16798-1 standard and following the air quality categories, the highest concentration reached class 3, which according to the standard would be category 2, because the outdoor CO₂ concentration, which is greater than 400 ppm, should also be taken into account, following the measured lowest recorded value in the auditorium [43].

Table 2 summarizes the output variable B1, showing the recorded minimum and maximum CO₂ concentration. The hourly distribution of CO₂ concentration (B1) in relation to the input variable A10 is illustrated in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. CO₂ concentration ranges for identical days and times, comparing the first week (ventilation off, upper limit), with the second week (ventilation on, lower limit)

During the generation of the decision tree for the dependent variable B2 across all analysed days of surveyed users (ventilation off – 2 days and ventilation on – 2 days) a total of 133 rules were generated. Classification accuracy ranged from 92.9% to 95.4% and the outcome probabilities (p) ranged from 0.667 to 1.000 for class 1; 0.571 to 1.000 for class 2 and 0.889 to 1.000 for class 3. When considering only days with ventilation off – 2 days, the decision tree for the dependent variable B2 generated 71 rules. Classification accuracy ranged from 89.2% to 95.8% with the outcome probabilities (p) between 0.667 and 1.000 for class 1; 0.700 and 1.000 for class 2 and 0.615 and 1.000 for class 3. During the generation of the decision tree for the dependent variable B2 when considering days of surveyed users (ventilation on – 2 days); 46 rules were generated. Classification accuracy ranged from 91.7% to 97.5% and the outcome probabilities (p) were between: 0.667 and 1.000 for class 1 and 0.700

and 1.000 for class 2. Since the presence of occupants is the principal determinant for ventilation operation, a decision tree model was developed incorporating a time-related variable (A10) that reflects the scheduled occupancy of the auditorium. This model was used to predict CO₂ concentration per class (B2) during periods when the space was occupied. The output variable B2 was examined through three distinct analyses: initially all data were analysed collectively (Fig. 8 a); subsequently, the dataset in conditions with the ventilation off (Fig. 8b) and the dataset in conditions with the ventilation on (Fig. 8c) were analysed, and the results are presented.

Figure 8. a) Distribution of variable B2 (CO₂ concentration per class) across all surveyed days of participating users (ventilation off - 2 days and ventilation on - 2 days); b) Distribution of variable B2 across days of surveyed users (ventilation off - 2 days); c) Distribution of variable B2 across days of surveyed users (ventilation on - 2 days)

By forcing the input variable A10, which branched the decision tree according to variables A5, A7 and A9, the analysis demonstrates that the specified activity (met) does not significantly influence CO₂ concentration. Under conditions when the external temperature is below 1.3 °C and ventilation off the model predicts a 92.3% to 100% probability that CO₂ concentration falls within class 3: [800 – 1350) ppm; (B2). Conversely, when the ventilation system is active, the predicted probability of CO₂ concentrations belonging to class 2 [550 – 800) ppm; (B2) ranges from 98.6% to 100%. For the dependent variable B3, the decision tree generated across all analysed days of surveyed users (ventilation off – 2 days and ventilation on – 2 days) resulted in 76 rules. Classification accuracy ranged from 96.3% to 99.2%, with the outcome probabilities (p) between: 0.571 and 1.000 for satisfactory “yes” and 0.600 and 1.000 for satisfactory “no”. During the generation of the decision tree for the dependent variable B3, when considering days of surveyed users (ventilation off – 2 days); 58 rules were generated. Classification accuracy ranged from 94.2% to 99.2%, with the outcome probabilities (p) between: 0.5 and 1.00 for satisfactory “yes” and 0.571 and 1.000 for satisfactory “no”.

The decision tree for the dependent variable B3 was not generated for days with ventilation on – 2 days, as the measured CO₂ concentration values were below 1000 ppm. For the output variable B3, the time-related variable A10, which corresponds to the scheduled period during which the space was anticipated to be occupied, was also enforced to examine the occurrences of CO₂ concentrations

exceeding 1000 ppm. The output variable B3 was analysed under two operating modes: first, all data were evaluated collectively (Fig. 9a), and then the subset corresponding to ventilation off conditions was examined (Fig. 9b), as no CO₂ concentrations above 1000 ppm were observed during ventilation on conditions.

Figure 9. a) Variable B3 (CO₂ concentrations yes - below 1000 ppm and no - above 1000 ppm) across all analyzed days of surveyed users (ventilation off - 2 days and ventilation on - 2 days); b) Variable B3 across days of surveyed users (ventilation off - 2 days)

In the case of the output variable B3, constraining the input variable A10, branched the decision tree towards variables A4, A5, and A9, revealing that these parameters significantly influence CO₂ concentrations when ventilation is *off*. Under these conditions, the model estimates an 80% to 100% probability that CO₂ concentrations (B3) will fall into class 2: ≥ 1000 ppm /no/.

The error estimation on the sample used for model training was performed using the Risk estimate indicator, which represents the proportion of misclassified cases in the total number of observations. In addition, the cross-validation method was applied to assess the extent to which the model can retain its predictive capability when applied to new, unseen data.

With ventilation enabled, for the dependent variable B2, the Risk estimate value was identical (0.242) for both the base model and the 10-fold cross-validation. When ventilation was disabled, the Risk estimate for B2 was 0.217 for the model, while it was 0.317 for the 10-fold cross-validation.

For the dependent variable B3, when ventilation was disabled, the Risk estimate value was identical (0.225) for both the model and the 10-fold cross-validation. The obtained results indicate that the model demonstrates relatively stable performance in predicting the dependent variables B2 and B3, without pronounced signs of model overfitting to the data.

Since the concentration measurements were obtained simultaneously with a survey of the students, it is essential to correlate their assessments of perceived air quality with the measured values. Moreover, it should also be noted that on the days when the measurements were conducted, the auditorium was occupied by, on average, one-third of its total seating capacity (maximum 66 users out of 194 seats), which likely contributes to the favourable air quality outcomes observed.

When the mechanical ventilation was off, the measured concentration exceeded 1000 ppm, and these conditions correspond to the first group of surveyed students/users. Therefore, their responses regarding air quality satisfaction were compared. The analysis of the surveys shows that 21.42% of respondents reported dissatisfaction with air quality (ratings of -3, -2, -1). When the mechanical ventilation was on 19.1% of respondents reported being dissatisfied. The difference of 2.32% suggests

that students did not perceive a meaningful change in air quality independent of the operation of the system of mechanical ventilation. Following the answers in the surveys, the students felt the difference in the internal temperature (a difference of 12.66%). Specifically, when the ventilation system was off, 25.39% of students were dissatisfied, whereas 12.73% reported dissatisfaction when the ventilation was on.

The CHAID model identified occupancy level, ventilation conditions, and time of space use as the dominant predictors of indoor CO₂ concentration, reflecting the balance between occupant emissions and air exchange processes. From a physical perspective, CO₂ accumulates due to occupants' metabolic activity, while its dilution depends on ventilation efficiency and room volume. These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting that indoor CO₂ levels in educational buildings are strongly influenced by occupancy patterns and ventilation conditions [10–12]. Furthermore, the observed relationship between perceived air quality and measured CO₂ levels is consistent with research suggesting that users are able to recognize changes in indoor air quality through subjective perception [13]. Decision tree-based approaches are particularly suitable for identifying such relationships because they provide transparent rule-based structures that facilitate interpretation of interactions between environmental and occupancy-related variables [24–26]. The CHAID algorithm further enables statistically significant segmentation of categorical variables using χ^2 tests [28, 29] and has been successfully applied in building-related studies to identify factors influencing building performance [30]. Although machine learning models such as neural networks may achieve higher predictive accuracy, their limited interpretability often reduces their practical usefulness compared to transparent tree-based approaches [27].

Although some machine learning models may achieve slightly higher predictive accuracy, the CHAID algorithm offers an important advantage in terms of model interpretability. The tree structure enables clear identification of threshold values and decision rules influencing indoor CO₂ concentration. This feature is particularly useful for practical applications in building management and ventilation control, where transparent and easily interpretable models are preferred. Overall, the obtained results support the findings reported in previous studies and demonstrate that data-driven approaches can effectively be used to analyze and predict indoor CO₂ concentration in educational and non-residential buildings.

4. Conclusion

The goal of this study was to predict CO₂ concentration levels in the auditorium of the new university building of the Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy and Faculty of Forestry (FACEG-FF) of the University of Banja Luka in correlation to the operation of the mechanical ventilation system. The data used for the analysis were collected by two sources: occupant surveys and measurements of physical parameters. Comparing the answers of the students, following the grades from 0 (neutral) to +3 (completely satisfied), it is notable that the students are overall satisfied. When the mechanical ventilation system is on, students are more satisfied with air temperature (87.3%) than with air quality (80.9%). When the system is off, satisfaction decreases for both parameters, to 78.6% for air quality and to 74.6% for air temperature, highlighting that the main effect of turning off ventilation is a general drop in comfort.

The indoor CO₂ concentrations during the first week (first survey - ventilation off) ranged from 453.35 to 1,141.24 ppm, while during the second week (second survey - ventilation on), they ranged from 456.8 to 834.8 ppm.

Classification accuracy was between 89.2% and 97.5% for dependent variable B2 (class of indoor air quality) and 94.2% and 99.2% for dependent variable B3 (satisfactory - value below or above 1000 ppm CO₂). The findings indicate that maintaining CO₂ levels below 1000 ppm is crucial for ensuring satisfactory indoor air quality and thermal comfort among occupants.

By forcing the input variable related to the time of use of the auditorium (A10), it is predicted that when the external temperature (A7) is lower than 1.3 °C and when the ventilation is *off* (A9), a probability of 92.3% to 100% is expected for CO₂ concentration class 3: [800 – 1350) ppm (B2), while when the ventilation is *on* (A9), a probability of 98.6% to 100% can be expected for CO₂ concentration class 2: [550 – 800) ppm (B2). When the mechanical ventilation system was *off*, the measured CO₂ concentration exceeded 1000 ppm (B3), corresponding to the first group of surveyed students/users.

The survey results indicate that students perceived a change in air quality through their subjective responses, consistent with what the objective measurements also demonstrated.

By demonstrating the effectiveness of the Chi-square Automatic Interaction Detection (CHAID) technique, this study provides a clear assessment of how physical parameters and occupant behavior influence CO₂ levels in a university auditorium. The primary contribution of this research lies in identifying the significance of these predictive factors, which is crucial for accurate CO₂ concentration forecasting. Beyond its theoretical value, this model offers a clear practical application: it can be directly integrated into ventilation control strategies to optimize indoor air quality and reduce energy consumption in enclosed spaces. While modern ensemble models like Random Forest and XGBoost dominate the literature due to their accuracy, CHAID was selected here for its high data interpretability, statistical significance, and reduced system complexity. Therefore, directions for further research indicate the need to employ alternative machine learning models and compare them against this baseline to evaluate the effectiveness of different modeling approaches and their potential for further accuracy gains.

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Nomenclature

IAQ – Indoor Air Quality	t – temperature [°C]
IEQ – Indoor Environmental Quality	S – Surface Area [m ²]
EU – European Union	v – Air velocity [m/s]
WHO – World Health Organization	<i>Greek letters</i>
DT – Decision Trees	χ^2 – Chi squared
CHAID – Chi-squared Automatic Interaction Detection	<i>Subscripts</i>
FACEG-FF – Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy and Faculty of Forestry	CO ₂ – Carbon dioxide [ppm]
VRV – variable refrigerant volume control	O _i – Observed numbers
ASHRAE – American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers	E _i – Expected numbers
ISO – International Standardization Organization	O _i – marginal frequency of the corresponding rows
MRT – Mean Radiant Temperature	O _j – marginal relative frequency
RH – Relative Humidity [%]	T _i – Indoor Air Temperature [°C]
Met – Metabolic rate	
Clo – Clothing insulation	

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